

Economic development – environmental issues

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ABSTRACT

Every developing country has been facing many socio-economic issues since its inception. The country has to make a way to find a solution for that. There is no doubt economic development is a universal drug for the issues. It can be considered that marginal increment in nation real income is in precise as economic development. But in this process hazardous waste is a byproduct. We cannot achieve even a product without this byproduct. The hazardous waste makes harm to environment and ecosystem. Human life is also part ecosystem. In the process of economic development many hazardous elements like SO₂, CO, Pb ect. Are polluting environment and it spoils ecosystem. Air is an essential element in the environment simply says no air, no life. The air pollution causes for human illness even deaths.

Key words: Economic development, dynamic process, GDP, Hazardous waste, Production factors, Goods and services

Introduction:

Even though growth is one of the characteristics in economic development, strictly speaking economic growth is not a synonym to economic development. They are different in nature of reference. The former term mainly focuses on qualitative aspects, the latter pays attention on quantitative aspects. Development is a dynamic process, it is spontaneous and discontinuous change in the channels of the flow, disturbance of equilibrium, which forever alters and displaces the equilibrium state previously existing (Joseph A Schumpeter, 1934). But while talking about the economic development of a country though it is qualitative character in nature, a quantitative character that is level of income will be taken in to consideration. For the augment in the magnitude of both characters depend reciprocally. Eg. Income levels enrich the qualitative characters, in the same way quality life can produce more output or income. It is convenient to take real GDP or output as a measuring rode keeping others constant for our discussion. R. F. Harrod defined growth in his growth theory that is

$$GC = S$$

G, which stands for growth, is the increment of total production in any unit period as a fraction of total production. The total production is the national income in terms of output. Therefore,

$$y = p$$

$$P = f(V)$$

$$V = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$$

Therefore,

$$G = \Delta p$$

$$\Delta p = \Delta V$$

To determine economic growth take partial derivative with respective production factors.. Rearrange the Equation

$$G = \Delta y = d(p)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dv} = \frac{dp}{dv} = G$$

Δv approaches to zero G also approaches to zero therefore G is a small change in the total production. Therefore,

$$\lim_{\Delta v \rightarrow 0} \frac{dy}{dv} = \lim_{\Delta v \rightarrow 0} \frac{dp}{dv} = G$$

Above Equation discloses the fact that the quantum of economic growth or development is the magnitude of production of goods. In spite of that the amount of economic growth can be decoupled with wastage which is generated along with goods in the production process at given technology. Hence, economic development can be expressed precisely based on the production function. The production function can be rearranged as

$$P = f(v)$$

$$P = g, w$$

$$g + w = f(v)$$

or

$$v = g + w$$

g stands for goods, w represents wastage. Therefore,

$$\Delta v = \Delta g + \Delta w$$

We know that economic development can be considered as a change in national real income or national output. But the enormity of national output depends on the size of inputs. The size of inputs is equal to the amount of goods and services which coupled with wastage as an output (goods and services) is just transformation of inputs in a process. Ranger Frisch divulges that the term transformation indicates that there are certain things (goods and services) which enter into the process and lose their identity in it i.e., ceasing to exist in their original form. Whole other things (goods and services) come into being in that they emerge from the process. The first category may be referred to as production factors (input elements) while the last – named category are referred as to products (output or resultant elements). The economic development is an increment in national output due to a change in production factors. In precise, it is

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta v} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial v} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial v} = G$$

Δv approaches to zero g and w also approach to zero therefore, intern G is a small change in the goods and services and wastage. Therefore,

$$\lim_{\Delta v \rightarrow 0} \frac{\partial y}{\partial v} = \lim_{\Delta v \rightarrow 0} \frac{\partial g}{\partial v} + \lim_{\Delta v \rightarrow 0} \frac{\partial w}{\partial v} = G$$

Above discussion ascertains that for economic development we have to pay the inherent cost of environment. It is clear that in the fast pace of rapid economic and population growth. There has been increasing demand for the natural resources over the last few decades for achieving the accelerated economic growth. Due to this reason natural resources have been extensively used which is adversely affecting the environment and biodiversity. Further, material use is also closely associated to with the problem of wastage (EnviStats, 2023).

Methodology:

The country has been considered as a unit for the study. The analysis in this paper depends on secondary data only.

Review of literature:

Dr.Dilip kumar nayak conducted a study on environmental pollution and its effects on health. He discussed the source of pollutants of air, water soil, noise pollution and he emphasized the need of immediate address of the issues. But he did not link up pollution and its issues with economic development.

Dr.Ramamanohar Reddy Appannagari opined that man is causing for damage of all elements of environment and to the ecosystem. He focused his attention on source of pollutions but he omitted the impact of environmental pollution on human beings.

Need for study:

Above studies are incomplete to make linkage between economic development and pollution and its effects on human health. It may be happened due to focus on all types of pollutions. Therefore there is a need to concentrate on single pollution and its impact on human health.

Objective:

1. To study air pollution and its effects on human health

.Data analysis:

The table ascertains the solid generation in municipalities of various states in the country. The state of Maharashtra stood first during the period 2021-22 with 82, 60,939 Tamil Nadu and Gujarat occupied second and third places in the same period with 48,99,031 and 37,86,433 tonnes respectively. The state Mizoram stood last in the descending order in solid waste generation with 1,26,097. Figure No.01 shows the collection of solid waste from the same states in the same period. The state of Chandigarh was the only state which collected cent per cent solid waste from the municipalities in the state. Maharashtra and Gujarat ran after Chandigarh respectively. The state Mizoram stood last not only in generation of solid waste but also in collection of the waste. However, the collection of solid waste is comparatively less than generation as a whole.

Table No.01**State wise municipal solid generation for 2021-22****(In Tonnes)**

Sl. No.	Name of the state	Solid waste generation
1	Rajasthan	25,17,464
2	Gujarat	37,86,433
3	Maharashtra	82,60,939
4	Tamil Nadu	48,99,031
5	Chandigarh	1,87,245
6	J&K	5,34,079
7	Mizoram	1,26,097

Source: enviStats2023, GoI

Figure No.01

State wise municipal solid collection for 2021-22

(In Tonnes)

Source: Table No. 01

The hazardous waste is harmful to the environment. It leads to resource depletion; environmental degradation affects economy, quality life and livelihood. Top ten hazardous waste generation states are given below.

The top ten states which are shown in the table generate together 91.24 per cent of hazardous waste, the remaining that is 8.76 per cent hazardous waste was generated by the rest of states in the country. Among the ten Gujarat was the topmost hazardous waste generation state in the country in 2022-23, it accounted for 40.39 per cent whereas the state of Telangana generated 2.28 per cent of hazardous waste. The only state Gujarat generated double digit per cent of hazardous waste in the period, the remaining had single digit value.

Table No.02

Top ten hazardous waste generation states in India during 2022-23

Sl. No.	Name of the state	percentage
1	Gujarat	40.39
2	Maharashtra	8.84
3	Andhra Pradesh	8.26
4	Rajasthan	7.92
5	Tamil Nadu	7.28
6	Odessa	7.12
7	Karnataka	3.4
8	Uttar Pradesh	3.14
9	Jharkhand	2.55
10	Telangana	2.28

Source: Central Pollution and Control Board, 2024, GoI

The amount of hazardous waste exists in a state may increase or decrease. It may be happened by import or export of hazardous waste in the state. If exports are more than the imports automatically the amount of waste will be less and vice versa. This scenario can be observed in below table.

It is clear that except Rajasthan remaining nine out of ten given states are importing state of hazardous waste. The state of Rajasthan in spite of exporting hazardous waste it imported the waste in the given period that is 2022-23. The state of Andhra Pradesh stood first with 1,67,589 MT. it was pursued by Karnataka and Tamil Nadu with 1,26,155 and 1,17,344 MTs respectively.

Table No.03
Imports and Exports of Hazardous waste in 2022-23
(In MT)

Sl. No.	Name of the state	Imports	Exports
1	Andhra Pradesh	1,67,589	0
2	Bihar	1,441	0
3	Gujarat	85,388	0
4	J&K	6,727	0
5	Karnataka	1,26,155	0
6	Madhya Pradesh	1,700	0
7	Punjab	847	0
8	Rajasthan	25,201	10
9	Tamil Nadu	1,17,344	0
10	West Bengal	41,777	0
	Total	5,74,169	10

Source: Central Pollution and Control Board, 2024, GoI

Environmental Issues:

The projected pace of economic development is going to put pressure on an already stressed and limited set of resources and may lead to resource depletion and environment degradation affecting the economy, livelihood and quality of life (EnviStats, 2023).

Table No.04
Year wise PM2.5 concentration

(μ/m^3)

Sl. No.	Year	Concentration
1	2018	72.5
2	2019	58.1
3	2020	51.9
4	2021	58.1
5	2022	53.3
6	2023	54.4
7	2024	50.6

Source: world most polluted countries, IQAir

The highest concentration of particulate matter 2.5(PM_{2.5}) μm^3 is recorded in 2018. In spite of some fluctuations in concentration values have been found in subsequent years the concentration value is less than that. It is however, down trend the concentration values regarding all years are more than the guidelines of WHO. The guidelines are shown below.

Table No.05
W.H.O guidelines

(PM 2.5 in μm^3)

Sl. No.	Concentration (μm^3)	Consideration
1	0-5	Good
2	5.1-10	Excess by 1 to 2 times
3	10.1-15	Excess by 2 to 3 times
4	15.1-25	Excess by 3 to 5 times
5	23.1-35	Excess by 5 to 7 times
6	35.1-50	Excess by 7 to 10 times
7	>50.1	Excess by more than 10 times

Source: world most polluted countries, IQAir

It is very clear that PM_{2.5} in all years which are given in the table NO.04 is more than 10 times as per the W.H.O guidelines which are shown in the table NO.05.

Air pollution and its impact:

Table No.06

Air pollution and its impact

Pollutant	Natural	Anthropogenic	Effect
SO ₂	Volcanic eruption	Combustion of fossil fuels	Respiratory illness, visual impairment, aggravation of existing heart and lung diseases Acidic rains
NO ₂	Lightening, Forest fires Bacterial activities of soils	Highest temperature combustion, burning of bio- mass fossil fuels	Irritating the nose and throat, increasing susceptibility respiratory infections
PM ₁₀	Windblown dust, Physical process of crushing, grinding and abrasion of surface. Non-combustible	Road traffic emissions particularly from diesel vehicles. Industrial combustion plants	Cardio pulmonary problems, Asthama, bronchitis

	materials released when burning fossil fuels	Commercial and residential , combustion, Non-combustion processing	
PM _{2.5}	Formally nucleation which the initial stage in which gas becomes a particle. Group of μ in either through condensation when additional gas condensates or coagulation	Vehicular emission , industrial source of PM ₁₀	Oxidation tress, respiratory problems, aggravate asthma, chronic bronchitis, irregular heartbeat, cardio- pulmonary disorder, premature death with heart or lung disease.
CO	Produced during normal animal metabolism in low quantities and has some normal biological functions Volcanic activity Forest bushfires	Exhaust of internal combustion engines. Especially of vehicles of petrol engines Burning of carbon fuels Organic combustion in waste incineration Power station Processes Iron smelting Burning of crop residuals	Person with heart disease are sensitive to CO poisoning and may experience chest pain Adverse effect on the fetus of a pregnant woman Infants, Elderly persons and individual with respiratory diseases are also particularly sensitive Anti-inflammatory, vasodilators and encourages of neovascular growth
Ozone	Ozone is present in the atmosphere, in a region also s the ozone layer between 10km and 50km above the surface	Formed by the reaction of sunlight on air coming hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides emitted by car engines, chemical solvents to form Ozone	Lung function deficits and respiratory illness Premature death, asthma, bronchitis, heart attack and other cardiopulmonary

		Electronic equipment such as photocopiers	problems Ground level ozone and pollution which interferes with photosynthesis and stunts overall growth of some plant species
Pb	Food (lead is absorbed by plants)	Waste incineration Metal processing Paint industry Lead solder in food cans, breast milk, drinking water, cosmetics, ceramic pottery, burning of fire wood or kerosene indigenous remedies, tobacco and tobacco products, contaminated drinking water, toys, industrial effluents, lead acid batteries, ammunition paint and varnishes, water pipes	Adverse effect on central nervous system, the cardiovascular system, kidneys and immune system Automobile exhaust Causes blood disorders like anaemia and increase in blood pressure Potent neurotoxin that accumulates both in soft tissues and the bones Causes nephropathy and colic-like abdominal pains Weakness in fingers, wrist or ankles Miscarriage and reduction of fertility in males, delayed puberty in girls Permanent reduce that cognitive capacity of children.

Source: National Ambient Air Quality status and trend 2019, CPCB, GoI, 2020

Death scenario in world due to air pollution during 2015-2021

The deaths due to air pollution were decreasing gradually during the given period that is 2015 to 2024. The highest deaths were recorded in 2015. The table ascertains the deaths in this year were 117.5 per lakh. Though the deaths were diminishing continuously by single digit in 2021 the deaths crept from 97.3 to 99.7.

Table No.07

Death scenario in world due to air pollution during 2015-2021

(Deaths per 100,000)

Sl. No.	Year	Deaths
1	2015	117.5
2	2016	114.3
3	2017	110.2
4	2018	106.3
5	2019	102.7
6	2020	97.3
7	2021	99.7

Source: IHME, Global Burden of Disease, 2024

We can find the deaths due to the pollutant PM 2.5 from 2018 to 2023 in below table.

Table No.08

Deaths due to PM 2.5 from 2018 to 2023

(Deaths per 100,000)

Sl. No.	Year	Deaths
1	2018	97.1
2	2019	83.3
3	2017	77.1
4	2018	76.9
5	2019	65.8
6	2020	79.9

Source: <http://en.wiki pedia.org>**Conclusion:**

It is concluded that economic development can be considered in precise as the magnitude of marginal national output in a particular period of time. It is essential for every developing country as it is a drug for many chronicle issues. No controversy in naming it as universal drug, but in the processes of making this drugs some byproducts namely hazardous waste are making harm to the environment. We know that no air, no life. As per the guidelines of WHO, PM_{2.5} should be 0-5 μm^3 , but the table 04 ascertains in India it is more than ten times. Table 07 and 08 show the deaths due to air pollution. We need environment friendly economic development

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